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Deontic logic for lawyers

Concepts without formalism

Jaap Hage

1 Introduction: Logical validity and deontic logic

- 1 Logic is the theory of valid reasoning. Traditionally, the notion of validity is given a precise meaning: an argument is logically valid if, and only if, it is logically impossible that all the premises of the argument are true, while the argument's conclusion is false. This definition is often supplemented with a model-theoretic characterisation of logical possibility.¹ In this paper, I will abandon the traditional approach. I will assume that an argument is logically valid if, and only if, it is rational for a person who accepts the premises of the argument to accept the argument's conclusion as well. Much can be said about the way in which this view of logical validity differs from the traditional one, but I confine myself to pointing out two differences. *First*, in the alternative approach logical validity is not defined in terms of truth. As a result, norms – which are not true or false – can be premises of valid arguments.² *Second*, an argument can be logically valid, even if the truth or validity of the premises does not guarantee the truth or validity of the conclusion. Rational acceptability is the standard, not truth.³
- 2 Deontic logic⁴ is the logic of what ought to be done, or what ought to be the case. This means that not all legal reasoning is governed by deontic logic. Examples of non-deontic reasoning in law are arguments about the validity of a rule, or about the legal classification of facts.⁵ It also means that there is deontic reasoning outside the realm of law. Moral reasoning is an obvious case in point. This paper only covers deontic logic as it is used in law.
- 3 Since a seminal paper by Von Wright, the field of deontic logic has been flourishing in the margins of formal logic in general and modal logic in particular.⁶ In this paper, I will attempt to bring deontic logic closer to the interests of theoretically interested lawyers. To that end, I will use examples of deontic reasoning that, although simplified for expository purposes, resemble real legal arguments.

- 4 Moreover, I will treat logic as a tool for human reasoners and will refrain from formalization. Most humans are not helped by the formalization of the standards for good reasoning. To the extent that formalization has added value, this value lies in the gain in precision. Precision is often desirable, but it can usually also be gained without the assistance of formalization.⁷
- 5 It is possible to distinguish three ‘steps’ of deontic reasoning, and these three steps structure the argument of this paper. The first step is from non-deontic facts to the duties (or obligations) an agent has. The second step is from these duties to what the agent (legally) ought to do. And the third step is from what an agent ought to do to whether an act performed by the agent was permitted, in the sense of lawful, or not.
- 6 Deontic logic is a broad subject, and I had to be selective in the topics that are addressed.⁸ The selected topics are the structure of ought-to-do facts (section 2); norms, duties, obligations, and what an agent ought to do (section 3); reasoning with norms (section 4); deontic inheritance (section 5); and three kinds of permission (section 6). The order of the discussion of these topics by and large follows the three steps outlined above.
- 7 A final remark in relation to the intended readership. The paper is aimed at theoretically interested lawyers and attempts to provide them with a readable introduction to deontic logic. It does not provide a description of deontic logic as an established field.⁹ In several respects – briefly mentioned in the conclusion – this paper takes positions that may be considered controversial. These positions are in this paper at most summarily defended and, to improve the readability of the main text, the defence often takes place in footnotes.¹⁰

2 The structure of ought-to-do facts¹¹

- 8 Deontic logic deals with what ought to be done and what ought to be the case, often referred to as respectively ought-to-do and ought-to-be.¹² In an ought-to-do statement¹³ there are three elements: a reference to the agent who ought to do something, a reference to an action the agent ought to perform or ought to refrain from,¹⁴ and a specification of whether the agent ought to perform the action, or whether (s)he ought to refrain from it (the action modality). For instance, if Alice ought not to damage her neighbour’s car, Alice is the agent, ‘damage her neighbour’s car’ is the action, and ‘refrain from’ is the action modality.
- 9 An example of an ought-to-be fact is that buildings ought to be white. In an ought-to-be fact, there are two elements: a state of affairs, and a deontic modality. In our example, the state of affairs is that ‘buildings are white’, and the deontic modality is that this is as it ought to be. The alternative deontic modality would have been that the buildings *ought not* to be white.
- 10 For law, ought-to-do is important, while ought-to-be is practically irrelevant. The reason for the latter is that an ought-to-be does not specify a person who is responsible for making sure that the state of affairs is as it ought to be.¹⁵ In our example: the mere fact that buildings ought to be white does not make anyone responsible for the colour of buildings. Law aims to guide the behaviour of agents, and an ought-to-be fact by itself is incapable of providing guidance.¹⁶ Because of its practical irrelevance for law, the logic of ought-to-be will not be discussed in this paper.¹⁷

2.1 Action types and act tokens

- 11 Deontic facts, such as the fact that John ought to halt for the red traffic light, have two functions: they aim to guide behaviour, and they provide standards by means of which the agent's behaviour can be evaluated. The primary function of the fact that John ought to halt is to make John halt for the traffic light. If the fact succeeds in this function and John actually halts, then John's behaviour can, to the extent that only the duty to halt is considered, be evaluated as lawful, correct, or even good. If John does not halt, his behaviour can be evaluated as *pro tanto*¹⁸ unlawful or incorrect. These evaluations are possible because of the standard for behaviour that is implicit in the fact that John ought to halt. Providing such a standard is the second function of an ought-to-do fact.¹⁹
- 12 The evaluation of acts is best conducted after the act has been performed, because one act can fall under more than one description – it can belong to more than one type – and then derives its ultimate evaluation from all the descriptions (types) under which it falls.²⁰ Suppose that John did not stop for a red traffic light because he wanted to make room for an ambulance that urged John to make room by means of its siren. John's act was not only ignoring a red traffic light but also making room for an ambulance. The evaluation should take both aspects into account. For this reason, evaluation should concern an act token, an act that was actually performed. Only then can all the act's properties be taken into account.
- 13 The guidance of behaviour can, in contrast, only be useful before the behaviour has taken place. If John already ran the red traffic light, the fact that he ought to halt cannot guide his behaviour anymore. Therefore, if John ought to halt for the traffic light, the action to which this applies should not yet have taken place. It cannot be an act token, since act tokens have been performed, by definition. It must be an action type: John ought to perform an, as yet indefinite, act of the type 'halt (for the red traffic light)'.²¹
- 14 As this example illustrates, it is important to distinguish between action types, and act tokens. Action types can exist, even if no concrete token of that type was ever performed. Guidance of future behaviour can only make sense if it refers to future behaviour of a particular type. Act tokens, in contrast, have already been performed. It does not make much sense to guide them anymore, but it is well possible to evaluate concrete acts by means of deontic facts such as that John ought to halt for the traffic light, or that John ought to make room for the approaching ambulance.
- 15 In the rest of this paper, I will use the word "action" for types, and the word "act" for tokens.

2.2 'Not ought' and 'ought not'

- 16 An ought-to-do fact refers to an agent and an action type but must also specify what the relation between the agent and the action type is. Is the agent to perform or refrain from performing the action type? In specifying that the agent ought to refrain from an action type, we often use the word "not". For instance, Donald ought not insult Joe. That can be misleading, as the word "not" is also used for negation. There is a meaning difference between "It is not the case that Donald ought to insult Joe" and "Donald

ought not insult Joe". The former sentence expresses that some ought-to-do fact does not exist, while the latter sentence expresses that some ought-to-do fact (dealing with refraining from an action) does exist. The former sentence expresses a 'not-ought', while the latter expresses an 'ought not'. In the former case, the 'not' expresses a negation, which makes a true sentence false and a false sentence true. In the latter case, the 'not' transforms one action type (performing an action) into another action type (refraining from an action). The word 'not' has different functions in the two sentences.²¹

- 17 The different functions of the word "not" have implications for deontic reasoning. To make this clear, it is useful to distinguish four situations:
1. Peter ought to vote.
 2. Peter ought not to vote.
 3. Peter neither ought to vote nor to refrain from voting.
 4. Peter both ought to vote and to refrain from voting.
- 18 Situation 4 is problematic since an agent cannot both perform an action and refrain from that action. However, it is not equally clear that this impossibility makes the co-existence of the two ought-to-do facts also impossible. Let us assume, for the sake of argument, that it is impossible that an agent both ought to perform some action and ought to refrain from that action. I will call that assumption *ought-to-do exclusion*. On the assumption of ought-to-do exclusion it is possible to derive from the fact that agent P ought to perform action A, that it is not the case (not ought) that P ought to refrain from A (ought not). It is also possible to derive from the fact that P ought to refrain from A that it is not the case that P ought to perform A. So, in terms of our example, given ought-to-do exclusion, it would be possible to derive the negation of sentence 2 from sentence 1.
- 19 Where situation 4 is problematic in the sense that it is not obvious that it can exist, situation 3 is completely unproblematic. It is very well possible that an agent neither ought to perform some action nor ought to refrain from that action. This means that the relation between an agent and an action type can be that the agent ought to perform the action type (situation 1), ought to refrain from the action type (situation 2), and neither ought to perform nor ought to refrain from that action type (situation 3). Any one of these situations can exist, but assuming ought-to-do exclusion and logical consistency, they are mutually exclusive, and from the existence of one of them the non-existence of the two other situations can be derived.

2.3 Acting in a particular way

- 20 A classical problem in deontic logic goes as follows:

Harry ought not to kill Christine.
 If Harry kills Christine, he ought to do so gently.
 Harry kills Christine.

 \therefore Harry ought to kill Christine gently.
 \therefore Harry ought to kill Christine.

- 21 This problem has become known as the "gentle murder paradox",²² because it seems to show that it is possible to derive a contradiction from seemingly uncontroversial premises. Many solutions have been proposed for this and seemingly related paradoxes in deontic logic.²³ The most attractive solution for the gentle murder paradox is to

acknowledge that there are two kinds of ought-to-do. The one kind is that an agent ought to perform an action; the other kind is that an agent ought to perform an action in a particular way. There is no logical relation between these two. To use a different example: if a cyclist ought to cycle on the right-hand side of the road, this does not imply that (s)he ought to cycle.

- 22 However, there is a complication with the ambiguity of sentences that express that an agent ought to do something in a particular way.

Suppose that Jaap has sold his home in the Netherlands to Petra. In the Netherlands there is a transfer system for the transition of property, which means that the sales contract between Jaap and Petra merely leads to two obligations. Jaap has the obligation to transfer the ownership of the home to Petra and Petra has the obligation to pay the price of the home to Jaap. In the Netherlands, contracts ought to be performed in good faith. So Jaap ought not only to transfer the home to Petra, he also ought to do so in good faith (in a decent manner). There are two ought-to-do facts involved: Jaap ought to transfer ownership of the home and Jaap ought to do so in good faith.

- 23 In this case, it can be derived from the fact that Jaap ought to transfer ownership in good faith that Jaap ought to transfer ownership. This case is therefore different from the situation where Harry ought to kill Christine gently but also ought not to kill her at all. The so-called gentle-murder paradox results from treating a case where there is only an ought for the way an action should be performed as if it were a situation where some action both ought to be performed and ought to be performed in a particular way. A deontic reasoner should be aware of this ambiguity and be careful not to conclude automatically that an agent ought to perform some action from the fact that the agent ought to perform that action in a particular way.

3 Norms, duties, obligations, and what an agent ought to do

- 24 Ought-to-do facts are, in a way that will be explained later in this section, a kind of summaries of the duties and obligations the agent has. These duties and obligations are in turn the output of rules, and especially norms.²⁴ Here we encounter, in reverse order, the first two steps of deontic reasoning.

3.1 Duties and obligations

- 25 There are basically two ways in which an agent can be obligated to do something or to refrain from doing something. First, the agent can have a duty, in which case there is no other person towards whom this duty exists, although it is possible that another person is the main beneficiary of the duty. This is different in the case of obligations; obligations are by definition directed.²⁵ If Louise promised (contracted with) Klara to lend her the copy of *Wuthering Heights* that Louise owns, then Louise has an obligation towards Klara to allow her the use of this book. Klara has a corresponding right (a claim) against Louise.

- 26 John may have the duty to stop before a white line because the traffic light is red. This duty is not a duty towards any person in particular. That may be obvious in a case when there is nobody else around, for instance because John is driving his car at 3am in a quiet countryside. It is, however, also the case when there is another driver on a crossing road who needs John to stop in order to be able to continue driving himself. This other driver may then be the main beneficiary of John's duty. Moreover, he may rely on the assumption that John will stop. Nevertheless, John's duty is not a duty towards this other driver, and the other driver has no right against John that John will stop.
- 27 For logical purposes, duties and obligations are highly similar. To avoid clumsy formulations like "duties or obligations", in the remainder of this paper I will focus on duties, but unless indicated otherwise, what I write about duties also holds for obligations.

3.2 Norms and duties (step 1)

- 28 Most duties are connected to the possession of a particular position, role or status.²⁶ It is, for instance, the duty of a judge to apply the law, and the duty of a home-owner to clear away the snow from the pavement in front of their home, and the duty of a car-driver to carry a driver's license. The connection between the possession of some position, role or status, for instance the role of car-driver, and a duty is brought about by a norm which attaches the duty to the position, role or status. An example would be the norm that car drivers (role players) must carry a driver's license. Another example is the (unwritten) norm that heads of states (holders of a position) owe a duty towards the citizens of their countries to protect their interests. A final example is that homeowners (possessors of a legal status) must pay real-estate tax.
- 29 The word "norm" is used in many senses. To avoid confusion, I will use the word here in the specific sense of a *mandatory rule*. So,
 Every person with an income shall (has the duty to) prepare a tax statement every year.
 is the formulation of a norm.
- 30 The main function of rules is to attach a fact to other facts.²⁷ The former fact is mentioned in the rule *conclusion*, while the latter facts are mentioned in the rule *conditions*. For instance, the rule about tax statements attaches the fact that Andrej has the duty to prepare a tax statement to the fact that Andrej is a person with an income.
- 31 Mandatory rules are characterised by the fact that they have the existence of a duty as their conclusion. In their conditions they usually specify the agents who can receive this duty.²⁸ Sometimes this specification of the agent seems to be lacking, as in
 It is forbidden to kill other persons.
 This appearance is deceptive because these rules also specify agents, but in their sources they do so implicitly.²⁹ In this example, all legal subjects are presumably the relevant agents.
- 32 Apart from specifying the agents of duties, norms often attach conditions to the creation of their duties. For instance, the norm
 If the government officially announces that there is a draught, farmers are not allowed to water their farmlands.

creates the duty for farmers to refrain from watering their lands, but only on the condition that the government has officially announced that there is a draught. This condition is mentioned in the rule conditions and is a condition for the existence of the duty. The duty itself is unconditional. So, if Aleida is a farmer, and the government has officially announced a draught, the unconditional conclusion is that Aleida has the duty not to water her farmland.³⁰

3.3 Duties and what an agent ought to do; conflicts of compliance (step 2)

- 33 An agent can have many duties and sometimes these duties conflict with each other. What the agent ought to do is, in a manner that will be discussed in more detail later, the result of these interacting duties. Let me give an example of conflicting duties.³¹

There is a norm that imposes a duty on farmers to combat thistles that grow on their land. Aleida is a farmer and because of the norm, Aleida has the duty to combat the thistles.

There is also a second norm, which prohibits all legal subjects from using pesticides. Aleida is also a legal subject and because of this second norm, Aleida has the duty not to use pesticides.

At first sight Aleida ought to combat thistles without using pesticides. Regrettably, the only way to combat thistles effectively is to use pesticides.³² Ought Aleida use pesticides to combat the thistles, or ought she refrain from using pesticides and violate her duty to combat the thistles?

- 34 The duties created by the two norms do not contradict each other in a logical sense. There is no logical relation between combatting thistles and the use of pesticides. The problem is the impossibility of complying with the duties that the two norms impose. The duties are *incompatible* and the agent who has both duties suffers from a *conflict of compliance*.³³ Conflicts of compliance and the incompatible duties from which they result cannot be solved by logic alone, and later we will see what additional information is required for deriving what Aleida ought to do. But even without this additional information, the problem can illustrate the difference between the duties that an agent has, and what the agent ought to do. The duties are directly the result of norms. As the example illustrates, it is possible to legislate in such a way that the result is that there are norms that impose conflicting duties. An agent faced with conflicting duties needs to determine what (s)he ought to do. If there were only one duty, the solution would be simple: the agent ought to act to conform with the duty.³⁴ But in the example there are two duties that cannot both be complied with – there is a conflict of compliance – and somehow both duties should be taken into account in determining what the agent legally ought to do. The method for doing that in a rational manner is the topic for section 3.4. For now, we can conclude that there is a difference between what an agent has the duty to do and what an agent ought to do. The duties are, metaphorically speaking, ingredients that are used to prepare the ought-to-do meal.³⁵
- 35 Even this simple result has implications for deontic reasoning. If an agent ought to perform some action, e.g. combat thistles by using pesticides, and also ought to refrain

from this action, there is a *logical* problem that needs to be solved.³⁶ That can, for instance, be done by assuming the ought-to-do exclusion. If an agent has a conflict of compliance, the agent has a problem, but that problem is *not logical*. The co-existence of incompatible duties (as opposed to incompatible ought-to-do's) is, logically speaking, very well possible. An agent who has incompatible duties must decide which duty (if any) to comply with. Such a decision can be made rationally by treating each of the duties as a reason why some action ought to be performed and by balancing these reasons.

For Aleida in our example this would boil down to the duty to combat thistles being a reason why she ought to combat the thistles by the use of pesticides. The duty not to use pesticides would be a reason why she ought to refrain from the use of pesticides. These reasons would need to be balanced to determine whether Aleida ought to refrain from using pesticides.

- 36 Balancing reasons is a metaphor. There is no set of scales on which heaps of reasons can be balanced to determine which heap weighs more. In the following subsection I will explain the logic of balancing reasons.

3.4 The logic of balancing reasons

- 37 The starting point for the logic of balancing reasons³⁷ is that for a particular claim there is a set of reasons that plead for the claim, the *pro-set*, and a set of reasons that plead against it, the *con-set*. These two sets need to be balanced. If the pro-set outweighs the con-set, the claim follows. If the con-set outweighs the pro-set, the negation of the claim follows. And if neither one set outweighs the other set, nothing follows and the conclusion remains indetermined.

In Aleida's case, there is one reason why she should use pesticides to combat thistles, namely that she has the duty to combat thistles and that using pesticides is the only way to comply with this duty.³⁸ If the claim around which the argument turns is that Aleida ought to combat the thistles, the pro-set for this thesis has one element, which is this reason. The con-set for this thesis also contains only one reason, namely that Aleida has the duty not to use pesticides. If the pro-set outweighs the con-set, Aleida ought to combat the thistles.³⁹ If the con-set outweighs the pro-set, it is not the case that Aleida ought to combat the thistles. And if neither set outweighs the other set, nothing follows.

- 38 The balancing of reasons for and against some conclusion is not a process; it is an argument with three premises. The first premise specifies the set of pro-reasons, the second premise specifies the con-set, and the third premise indicates which of these two sets, if any, outweighs the other set.

In Aleida's case, the thesis might be that Aleida ought to combat the thistles on her land.

- The pro-set for this thesis would be: {Aleida has the duty to combat the thistles}.
- The con-set against this thesis would be: {Aleida has the duty not to use pesticides}.⁴⁰

- The weighing knowledge might be that the con-set outweighs the pro-set. And then the conclusion would be that it is not the case that Aleida ought to combat the thistles on her land (not ought).

- 39 The two premises that specify the pro- and the con-set will themselves be the conclusions of arguments that justify the existence of each of the reasons in the set, and arguments that show that these reasons are the only ones. In Aleida's case, one thing that needs to be shown is that there is a duty for Aleida to combat the thistles and that this is a reason to combat the thistles.⁴¹ Another thing that needs to be shown is that there are no other reasons that plead for the thesis.⁴²
- 40 How the balance of reasons for and against a thesis works out depends on their relative weight. The question of what set of reasons outweighs the other set may be answered by just cutting the knot; a legal reasoner can take a decision without having special reasons why this decision is better than its alternative. In that case, the claim about the relative weight of the reasons is a premise of the full argument. It can also be answered by an argument about the relative weight of the reasons for and against application. The claim about the relative weight would then be an intermediate conclusion of the full argument.
- 41 Reasoning about the relative weight of sets of reasons is important in law, but it is not a topic for deontic logic. That is why the general discussion about relative weight is not dealt with in this paper.⁴³ There is one important exception, however. There are often only reasons that plead for (or against) a thesis, and no reasons pleading in the other direction. If that is the case, the 'balancing' is easy: the existing reasons determine what the conclusion is.⁴⁴

So, if there were no duty to combat thistles, Aleida would only have a reason against the use of pesticides (the duty not to use them) and this reason would 'outweigh' the empty set of reasons. The outcome would be that Aleida ought to refrain from using pesticides.

3.5 Deontic reasons

- 42 We have seen that balancing reasons is not a process, but a conclusion based on a premise or intermediate conclusion about the relative weight of the reasons for and against the final conclusion. It is now time to address another topic, namely, what the reasons for or against a conclusion are. What kinds of entities are reasons?
- 43 The question of what reasons are has no simple answer, if only because there are different kinds of reasons such as reasons for believing something (epistemic reasons), reasons in the sense of causes (e.g. the reason why the doorbell did not ring), and reasons why something is the case (constitutive reasons).⁴⁵ Here the focus will be on reasons why something is the case, that is constitutive reasons. Specifically, we will take a closer look at reasons why somebody has the duty (not) to perform some type of action. Let us call these constitutive reasons *deontic reasons*.
- 44 A brief answer to the question of what deontic reasons are is that deontic reasons are (1) facts, which (2) are relevant for the issue of whether a specific agent has the duty (not) to perform some kind of action.

The reason why Dolly has the duty not to insult Jolene is that Jolene is a human being. If Jolene would have been a dangerous snake, there would not have been a reason why Dolly has the duty not to insult Jolene (to the extent that it is even possible to insult snakes).

- 45 Deontic reasons are relevant for the existence of a duty. The fact that Jolene is a human being is relevant to Dolly's duty not to insult her because of a norm that prohibits insulting human beings.

4 Reasoning with norms (step 1 revisited)

- 46 Norms are important for the existence of deontic reasons, because they spell out the types of facts that count as reasons for the existence of duties. These duties, in turn, determine what an agent ought to do. Norms are rules and rules are not statements or propositions. They are neither true nor false, and it is impossible to apply classical logic to them. This section rather apodictically describes *Rule Logic*, a logic for reasoning with rules that assigns a central role to the balancing of reasons for and against the application of a rule.⁴⁶ The logic of norms is the logic of rules, and the defining characteristic of norms – that their conclusions are that some duty exists – plays no role in the logic of norms. Rule Logic is the logic for all rules, including norms.

4.1 Rule Logic

- 47 The starting point for Rule Logic is that rules are immaterial logical *individuals* (things). In this respect they are comparable to organisations, numbers, or musical compositions. A rule can exist during a stretch of time, it can be created and be destroyed (abolished), it can be liked or disliked, etc. A rule that exists is said to be *valid*.⁴⁷
- 48 A rule is *applicable* to a case (a set of facts) if the rule is valid and if the facts of the case satisfy the conditions of the rule.⁴⁸ For example, the rule that everybody has the duty not to insult human beings is valid and is applicable to all cases that involve human beings.
- 49 A rule can *apply* to a case, and then it attaches its conclusion as a new fact to the case facts. For example, if the rule that everybody has the duty not to insult human beings applies to the case of Dolly and Jolene, it imposes on Dolly the duty not to insult Jolene.
- 50 A rule applies to a case if, and only if, the reasons why the rule applies to that case outweigh the reasons why the rule does not apply. If a rule is applicable to a case, this is a reason why the rule applies to that case. This reason (and eventual other reasons for application) needs to be balanced against potential reasons against application. If there are no reasons against application – which is the most common situation – the applicability of the rule guarantees application.⁴⁹
- 51 Which facts count as reasons against the application of a rule to a case is not a matter of logic. In the case of legal rules, the law determines which reasons count against the application of a rule.⁵⁰ Reasons against application that are sometimes mentioned are that the application of a rule would be against the purpose of the rule, or that there is

another applicable rule with a conclusion that is incompatible with the conclusion of the rule at issue. The latter case will be discussed here under the heading of conflicting norms.⁵¹

4.2 Conflicting norms

- 52 The balancing of reasons is not only important if there are incompatible duties, but also to avoid an agent having incompatible duties in the first place. To illustrate this (and to avoid overburdening the example of Aleida), I will use the following example:

John drives his car and approaches a red traffic light. He wants to halt for the traffic light, but then he hears the siren of an approaching ambulance. John knows that he has the duty to make room for the ambulance, but he can only do so by proceeding through the red traffic light. What ought he to do?

- 53 There are two ways to deal with situations like this.⁵² One way solves John's problem on the level of norms. There are two conflicting norms and one of them needs to be set aside. Then there is only one duty left for John, with which he ought to comply. The other way is to accept that the conflicting norms both apply and generate conflicting duties for John. Then the duties need to be balanced to determine what John ought to do. The second approach was discussed in section 3.3. The first approach is the topic of the present section.
- 54 In John's case, two norms are involved. One norm is that traffic participants have the duty to halt for red traffic lights; the other norm is that traffic participants have the duty to make room for approaching ambulances. Both norms are valid (let us assume), and the conditions of both norms are satisfied by John's case. Therefore, both norms are applicable to the case. So, for both norms there is a reason why they apply to the case and create a duty for John.
- 55 The duties that would be created if both norms would apply are that John should halt for the traffic light and that John should make room for the ambulance. These duties can co-exist but given the circumstances they cannot both be complied with. This conflict of compliance suggests a way to avoid John's dilemma. Both norms are applicable to the case, so for both norms there is a reason why they apply and why they create a duty for John. However, for both norms there is also another applicable norm which, if it would apply to the case, would create an incompatible duty. The existence of an applicable conflicting second norm is a reason not to apply the first norm. The applicability of the norm about ambulances is a reason not to apply the rule about red traffic lights, and the other way round.
- 56 The incompatibility of the duties and the conflict of compliance to which the norms would lead if they were both applied makes it such that for both norms there is a reason why it applies (the norm is applicable) and a reason why it does not apply (application would lead to a compliance conflict). These reasons need to be balanced. The outcome determines which norm applies and which duty comes into existence. Whatever the outcome will be, there will be only one duty and no incompatible duties. John's conflict of compliance is avoided.

4.3 Conflicting obligations

- 57 For logical purposes, duties and obligations are very similar. It is therefore interesting to point out a situation where there seems to be a difference.⁵³ The fact that the application of rules would lead to conflicting obligations (obligations that lead to a conflict of compliance) is *not* a reason why the applicability of one rule would be a reason why the other rule does not apply.
- 58 Suppose, for instance, that Jaap sold his home both to Petra and to Wojciech. According to Dutch law, both sales contracts lead to an obligation to transfer the home to the buyer. The home can be transferred only once, so there is a conflict of compliance. Is the fact that a second sale (before the home was transferred to the first buyer) would lead to this conflict of compliance a reason why the second sale does not lead to an obligation? In Dutch law that would not be the case, at least not in general. Both sales contracts lead to obligations, and the conflict of compliance must be solved by a transfer of the home to one buyer, and compensation of damage to the other buyer. So, apparently, only the second solution mentioned in section 4.2 is available in the case of obligations.⁵⁴

5 Deontic inheritance (reasoning on the level of ought-to-do)

- 59 If an agent ought to perform some type of action and if performing an act of that type necessarily means that the agent also performs an act of another type, does this mean that the agent also ought to perform the latter type of action? For example, if a farmer ought to remove thistles from his land and if doing so makes using pesticides necessary, does this mean that the farmer ought to use pesticides? This is but one example of a kind of reasoning that falls under the heading of “deontic inheritance”. The study of deontic inheritance deals with the way in which close relations between action types lead to logical relations between ought-to-do facts and permitted-to-do facts⁵⁵ involving these action types.

5.1 When one type of action involves another type

- 60 The most obvious case of deontic inheritance is when an agent ought to perform an action type and this action type involves another action type.⁵⁶ An example is that playing blindfold chess involves playing chess. Blindfold chess is playing chess without being able to see the chessboard. It is impossible to play blindfold chess without also playing chess.
- 61 One logical consequence of this impossibility is that if an agent ought to play blindfold chess (s)he also ought to play chess. A second consequence is that if an agent ought to refrain from playing chess (s)he also ought to refrain from playing blindfold chess. In this connection four things should be noticed:
- 62 (1) If action-type₁ involves action-type₂, the fact that an agent ought to perform action-type₁ brings along – and makes it possible to derive – that the agent also ought to perform action-type₂. For instance, an agent who ought to play blindfold chess ought to play chess.

63 (2) If action-type_1 involves action-type_2, the fact that an agent ought to refrain from action-type_2 also means that the agent also ought to refrain from action-type_1. For instance, an agent who ought to refrain from murder ought to refrain from poisoning.

64 (3) An action type that consists in performing another action type in a particular manner (e.g., playing chess without seeing the chessboard) only involves the latter action type if it is *both* performing the latter action type and performing it in a particular manner. For instance, both playing chess and playing chess without seeing the board.

More generally, the relations between action types that count as involvement can have different natures. For instance, they can be conceptual, such as the relation between playing blindfold chess and playing chess. Or they can be causal, such as the relation between poisoning a person and killing this person. They can be very strong, as in the blindfold chess example, or weaker, as in the example about poisoning.⁵⁷

65 (4) The relation between action types translates into a relation between facts of the ought-to-do type. It is not obvious that it also translates into a relation between *duties*. If an agent has the duty to play blindfold chess, does this mean that (s)he also has the duty to play chess? The answer seems to depend on how the existence of a duty is connected to the source of the duty, for instance a norm. If there is a norm that imposes the duty to play blindfold chess, does this norm also impose the duty to play chess? It depends on how one sees duties and this is an issue that common parlance does not solve.⁵⁸

5.2 Recurrent duties and one-shot duties

66 Some duties can be complied with once and for all. An example of such a *one-shot duty* is the duty to return a stolen object. After the good has been returned, the duty has ended. Other duties continue to exist after they have been complied with at a particular occasion. The duty to prepare a yearly tax statement would be an example of such a *recurrent duty*. Preparing a tax statement one year does not free one from the duty to prepare another statement the next year and the following years.

67 Arguably, there is more than one duty involved in the case of recurrent duties. In the first place there is the recurring duty to prepare a yearly tax statement. In the second, third, ... etc., place there are specific one-shot duties to prepare the statement for that year. On this view, the relation between recurrent duties and the one-shot duties that result from it is a special case of deontic inheritance. The recurrent action type 'preparing yearly tax statements' involves the one-shot action type 'preparing the tax statement for year ...'. The (recurrent) duty to perform the recurrent action type then leads to duties to perform the one-shot action types each year, which would be a case of deontic inheritance.

5.3 When acts of one agent count as the acts of another agent

68 Sometimes the acts of one agent *count as* the acts of some other agent. An example is when the juridical acts of a representative of an organisation count as the juridical acts of the organisation. The contract in which a sales representative of a company enters counts as the sales contract that company entered into.

- 69 Such a counts-as relation can also be seen as a case of one action type involving another action type. The actions of a representative involve actions of the represented organisation. So, at first sight, if an organisation ought to refrain from – for example – selling alcoholic beverages to children, this means that the sales representative also ought to refrain from doing so.
- 70 So far so good, but the law also has an alternative solution for such problematic actions: it can deny the counts as-relation between the act of the representative and the acts of the organisation. If a liquor shop sales representative sells alcoholic beverages to children, the acts of the sales representative do not count as acts of the liquor shop. The former actions were *ultra vires*. They do not involve the latter's actions, and the issue of deontic inheritance no longer plays a role.

6 Permission

- 71 The notion of permission in deontic logic is rather tricky.⁵⁹ I will distinguish three senses in which the notion is used: weak permission, strong permission, and token-permission. I will also distinguish something that is closely related to a strong permission, namely a freedom.

6.1 Weak permissions

- 72 It is sometimes claimed that everything that is not forbidden is permitted. In one sense of “permitted”, this claim is true by definition. Sometimes the fact that some type of action is permitted for an agent just means that this type of action is not forbidden for that agent. For example, if it is not forbidden for Max to drive a car, it is permitted for Max to drive a car. This kind of permission will be called ‘weak permission’.
- 73 Just like the ought facts the existence of which they deny, *weak permissions* always deal with *action types*, never with act tokens. A weak permission for a type of action is nothing other than the absence of a duty to refrain from that type of action. Weak permissions can always be replaced by the absence of an ought fact, and *vice versa*.
- 74 Given the nature of weak permissions, they cannot be created by a norm. As a matter of fact, they cannot be created at all, because they are in a sense nothing.⁶⁰

6.2 Strong permission

- 75 In the fictional world of James Bond movies, there is a rule that secret agents whose code number starts with “00” have a permission to kill other persons in their professional role. Since James Bond has “007” as his code number, this permissive norm gave James Bond the permission (license) to kill.⁶¹ That permission is a so-called ‘strong permission’.
- 76 The main, if not only, purpose of strong permissions is to make exceptions to prohibitive norms. There is, let us assume, a general prohibitive norm against people killing other people. So, barring his special license, there would be a duty for James Bond not to kill other human beings. The license (strong permission) for James Bond to kill is a reason why the prohibitive norm does not apply to him, even if it is applicable. Since the permissive rule is a *lex specialis* to the general prohibition, the permission

outweighs the prohibition.⁶² As a result, the norm that prohibits killing other people does not apply to James Bond, and for the movie hero there is no duty based on this norm not to kill.

- 77 Just like weak permissions, strong permissions deal with action types. However, where weak permissions have nothing to add to the absence of duties – they are strictly speaking superfluous – strong permissions do have a function: they block the application of prohibitive norms and prevent duties to refrain from even coming into existence.

6.3 Freedoms

- 78 *Freedoms*, such as the freedom of expression, are not permissions strictly speaking, but they are closely related to strong permissions. One way to look at freedoms is as a legal status to which the law attaches more elementary consequences, such as duties or strong permissions.⁶³ Typically, a freedom holder has a strong permission to perform some type of action. An example would be a strong permission to express one's (political) opinion. Such a permission can block prohibitions against several types of behaviour, not only the prohibition to express one's opinion. The freedom of expression may, for example, also block a prohibition against distributing flyers in the marketplace. Precisely which norms are blocked by this freedom is a matter of law, not of logic.

6.4 Token-permission (step 3)

- 79 At this point we have already encountered two kinds of permission. Weak permission is nothing (other than the absence of an ought-fact). Strong permissions make exceptions to prohibitive norms. However, there is still a third kind of permission, which deals with act tokens. The best way to introduce these *token-permissions* is by the re-use of an example in a slightly modified form.

There are two norms. One norm imposes a duty on farmers to combat thistles. The other norm prohibits the use of pesticides. As it turns out, the only way to combat thistles is to use pesticides. Aleida is a farmer, and she wonders whether her use of pesticides to combat thistles was lawful.

- 80 The first thing to note about this example is the question that is raised. It is not whether the use of pesticides to combat thistles is lawful. That would be a question about an action type. The question is about the lawfulness of what Aleida actually did; it is a question about an *act token*. At minimum, this token has the characteristics that it was an instance of combatting thistles and an instance of using pesticides, but unavoidably it also has many other characteristics, such as trying to earn a living, using particular machines, going out on a sunny day, and so on. The evaluation of the act as lawful or unlawful⁶⁴ depends in principle on *all* characteristics of the act. Most of those characteristics will be legally irrelevant, but some of them will be relevant.

The relevant characteristics in the example about Aleida will include that the act was an instance of combatting thistles and an instance of using pesticides, but there are potentially more legally relevant characteristics.

- 81 All legally relevant characteristics play a role in determining the lawfulness of the act. Most of these characteristics will be reasons that plead directly for or against the lawfulness of the act. However, some legally relevant facts can influence the relative weights of these reasons. In the end, *the (un)lawfulness of the act is the outcome of balancing the reasons for and against lawfulness*. Although this is almost a platitude, it structures the way we can argue about the lawfulness of act tokens.⁶⁵

6.5 Deontic inheritance of permissions

- 82 With the distinctions between the three kinds of permission in place, we can look back at the phenomenon of deontic inheritance. If one type of action involves a second type, does this have implications for the permission to perform the involved action types?
- 83 With regard to *token-permission* I can be brief. An act token will normally instantiate several action types and will not be a token of one action-type in particular. Deontic inheritance is based on involvement relations between action types and is therefore not well-defined for act-tokens.
- 84 For deontic inheritance regarding *weak permission* I can also be brief. Strictly speaking, a weak permission is nothing, and specifically it is not a deontic status. The issue of deontic inheritance does therefore not play a role with regard to weak permission.
- 85 What about deontic inheritance for *strong permission*? The typical function for a strong permission is to make an exception to a prohibitive norm. The example used earlier is the permission for secret agents to kill. Deontic inheritance for a strong permission would mean that if the permitted behaviour involves some other action type, this other type would also be strongly permitted, or the other way round.
- 86 Let us consider what this means for an adapted version of the gentle murder case. Committing a gentle murder involves committing a murder. If James Bond has a strong permission to perform gentle murders, does this imply that he has a strong permission to commit murders? It seems not. Committing murders in general is a broader category than committing gentle murders and a strong permission to commit actions of the restricted category (gentle murders) would not be a strong permission for the broader category.
- 87 Perhaps it is the other way round then? If James Bond has a license to kill, does he also have a license to kill gently? That seems more likely, but it becomes immediately dubious if the example is modified a little. Does the license to kill imply a license to kill cruelly? It seems not. However, the difference between the two situations seems to be only moral, not logical. Apparently, the precise conditions under which deontic inheritance for strong permissions is possible requires additional research.

7 Conclusion

- 88 These open-ended considerations on the deontic inheritance of permissions conclude my attempt to present deontic logic in a manner that is useful for theoretically interested lawyers. I have taken an unconventional approach to deontic logic. First, I have made no attempt to formalize my account of deontic logic. Second, I did not treat deontic logic as a branch of, or a variation on, alethic modal logic (the logic of necessity and possibility). I do not believe that the logic of what ought to be done, or to be refrained from, is very similar to alethic modal logic. These differences are related, because the usual formalizations of deontic logic make use of so-called *deontic operators*, which strongly pushes it into the direction of modal logic.
- 89 Other reasons for my less than conventional approach have to do with the details of my account of deontic logic. These details include:
- (a) the division of deontic reasoning into three steps: norm application, reasoning about the relations between ought-to-do facts (in particular deontic inheritance), and reasoning from the deontic status of action types to the evaluation of act tokens;
 - (b) the emphasis on the ought-to-do facts type, and disregard of ought-to-be facts;
 - (c) the emphasis on two functions of deontic facts: guiding future behaviour and evaluating past acts;
 - (d) that the logic does not use ‘deontic operators’, which are out of place in a logic for ought-to-do;
 - (e) the central role assigned to the distinction between action types and act tokens;
 - (f) the distinction between, on one hand, duties and obligations and, on the other hand, facts of the ought-to-do type;
 - (g) the treatment of duties and obligations as reasons for what an agent ought to do, rather than as some weakened form (*prima facie*, or *pro tanto*) of ought-to-do;
 - (h) the claim that the logic of norms is the logic of rules in which the deontic component of norms plays no role of logical importance;
 - (i) the strict distinction between descriptive statements and rules, leading to a distinct logic for rules (Rule Logic);
 - (j) the central role assigned to the balancing of reasons in arguments about norm-application, about the step from duties to what an agent ought to do, and about the step from what action types an agent ought to do or to refrain from to evaluations of act tokens as (un)lawful;
 - (k) the discussion of deontic inheritance as a tool for drawing conclusions about what an agent ought to do from involvement relations between action types;
 - (l) the distinction between three kinds of permission, where two of the kinds are connected to action types and one is connected to act tokens.

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NOTES

1. A traditional account of the model-theoretic approach to logical validity can be found in Smith 2012: 242-263.
2. Earlier attempts to develop a logic for norms without truth values are Alchourrón and Martino 1990 and Hage 1997.
3. What precisely counts as rational acceptability must be left open here. To indicate the direction that my answer would take: what is rational depends on the standards used in a community of reasoners, and on the practices of a social group. Rationality would not be an *a priori* notion then.
4. The word “deontic” is derived from the Greek *déon*, which stands for “what is binding”, or “proper” (Hilpinen and McNamara 2013). There is a close relation between what is deontic and what ought to be done or ought to be the case, but the relation is not so close that the deontic can be identified with the ought. Footnote 16 mentions an illustrative example.
5. Even though these arguments are not deontic themselves, considerations of what ought to be done may play a role in, for instance, the legal classification of facts. This is not the place to discuss that topic, however.
6. The ‘seminal paper’ is Von Wright 1951. Other important publications in the formal tradition include Von Wright 1963, Alchourrón and Bulygin 1971, Hilpinen 1971 and 1981, Horty 2001, Gabbay *et al.* 2013 and 2021, and Navarro and Rodríguez 2014, but this list is far from exhaustive.

7. If logic is used as an instrument for artificially intelligent systems, the mentioned reasons why the theory has not been formalised may not apply. There may be a role for formalized logic, but this role is not to assist human reasoners.
8. An important topic that will hardly be addressed here (but see section 5.2) is the role of time in the rise and disappearance of duties. Time will not be discussed, because it seems that the logic of temporal development of normative positions such as duties or permissions is independent from the deontic aspects of reasoning.
9. The best presently available overview of formal approaches to deontic logic is, to my knowledge, the two volumes of the Handbook of Deontic Logic and Normative Systems (Gabbay *et al.* 2013 and 2021).
10. Readers who are interested in a more elaborate exposition of this paper's views can consult Hage 2018: *passim*.
11. I assume here that there can be deontic (ought-to-do) facts. Not because I believe that deontic facts exist objectively, but because I assume that a fact is what is expressed by a true descriptive sentence and that sentences such as 'John ought to halt for the traffic light' aim to describe and can be true.
12. This distinction was emphasized in Castañeda 1972.
13. In this paper I will freely move between deontic statements and deontic facts without paying much attention to the difference. For the present purposes this does not matter very much.
14. In section 2.3 there will be a brief discussion of *the way in which* an agent ought to perform some type of action.
15. Legislation can contain provisions to the effect that something ought to be the case. For instance: 'Administrative dispositions ought to be in writing'. Such provisions are not deontic in the sense that they prescribe behaviour or indicate what ought to be the case. In this particular example, the law attaches a consequence (presumably: invalidity) to the absence of a situation and uses an ought-formulation to specify that situation. More in general: the English language uses the word 'ought' for many purposes (White 1975: ch. 10), and not all of them are action-related and deontic. For a discussion of the relation between ought-to-be and ought-to-do and the role of responsibility in that connection, see Brouwer 1990: 72-76.
16. It may be argued that this is different if it ought to be the case that somebody performs some action. But even then, the fact that it ought to be the case that John halts for the red traffic light does not make John responsible for halting. That would be different if John ought to halt for the traffic light (an ought-to-do fact). This point is important, because there is a branch of deontic logic that analyses ought-to-do facts as ought-to-be facts about an agent performing an action. For a discussion, see Horty 2001, 44-46.
17. Readers who are interested in the logic of ought-to-be can start from so-called Standard Deontic Logic. See, for instance, McNamara and Van de Putte 2022: sec. 2.
18. Insertions such as *pro tanto*, or the more old-fashioned *prima facie*, reflect that ought-to-do facts can be the outcome of several factors, such as duties, obligations, or exceptions to norms. Often it is useful to say what ought to be done without being able to take 'everything' into account. Then a *pro tanto*-clause indicates that what ought to be done is a conclusion based on a possibly incomplete set of reasons.
19. If duties (and obligations) guide behaviour, it is not rules that perform this function. If norms are defined as a kind of rules – which I will do later in this paper – norms do not guide behaviour either, at least not directly.
20. See section 6.4.
21. In the literature on deontic logic, this distinction is sometimes referred to as the distinction between internal and external negation. The former would indicate that an action type ought to be refrained from – $O(\sim\text{action})$ – while the latter denies that an agent ought to do something: $\sim O(\text{action})$. In my opinion, this terminology is misleading, as the “not” in the internal negation

does not negate anything, but indicates that the ought refers to refraining from some action. That is why I used two different operators (\sim and \neg) for the negation of an ought-statement (not ought), respectively the transformation from an action to its complement (from do to refrain).

22. Forrester 1984.

23. These ‘seemingly related’ paradoxes are based on so-called ‘contrary-to-duty obligations’, duties that result if some other duty has been violated. Contrary-to-duty obligations are notoriously hard to handle in Standard Deontic Logic. See Hage 2001.

24. It is theoretically possible that a duty exists as a conventional fact for which no norm is required, and for which broad recognition suffices. See Hage 2022. That possibility will be ignored in this paper. The words and expressions ‘rule’, ‘norm’, ‘duty’, ‘obligation’, and ‘ought-to-do’ are in common parlance used in many related but different senses, and an attempt to follow this ordinary usage will therefore be fruitless. In this section, I will give these words a precise meaning which does not deviate too much from how these words are ordinarily used, but which at the same time cannot completely coincide with common parlance, which lacks the desired precision.

25. The account of obligations that is presented here is based on the tradition of Roman law. In the common law there is no sharp distinction between, for instance, contractual obligations and duties that are not directed specifically towards some person. As a consequence, the meanings of ‘duty’ and ‘obligation’ in the English language hardly differ. See also Hage 2018: 123-126.

26. White 1984: 21-26.

27. See Hage 2018: ch. V, and Hage 2022 and 2024 for an explanation of this apodictic claim.

28. Here obligations differ from duties. The content of duties is determined by the rules that impose these duties. Obligations are the result of events to the occurrence of which the law attaches the existence of an obligation as a consequence. This event usually also determines the content of the obligation. For instance, the content of a contract determines the obligations resulting from the contract, including the debtor (and the creditor) of the obligation. The damage resulting from a tort determines the precise content of the obligation to compensate the damage, again including the debtor and the creditor.

29. In this connection it is important to distinguish between the rule as a logical structure with an unambiguous rule formulation that mentions the rule’s condition and a conclusion, and the source from which the rule stems. This source can have many different forms, and it is, for instance, possible that one statutory provision creates more than one rule, or that a single rule is based on more than one provision.

30. The distinction between mandatory rules (norms), which are conditional, and the duties based on them, which are not conditional, makes debates on how conditional ought-facts should be formalized (e.g. $p \rightarrow Oq$ vs $O(p \rightarrow q)$) superfluous. This is so, even apart from the question of whether such formalisations make sense if we are writing about ought-to-do.

31. The example was adapted from Brouwer 1990.

32. I do not know if this is true, but I will assume it for the sake of the example.

33. Goble 2013 provides a technical logical discussion of these conflicts of compliance under the name of normative conflicts.

34. This is simple because of the rule that any non-empty set of reasons outweighs the empty set. See section 3.4.

35. What is discussed here under the heading of the distinction between duties and ought-to-do has a counterpart in the distinction that is traditionally made between *prima facie* (or *pro tanto*) duties and duties all things considered (*sans phrase*) (Ross 1930: 19). I do not follow this traditional usage because the duties are not *pro tanto* or *prima facie*. They are definitive, full-blown duties. However, these duties may nevertheless have to give in if there is a conflict with incompatible other duties, and they do not therefore necessarily lead to an ought-to-do fact.

36. The claim here that the nature of the problem is logical is not without issues. That has not to do with incompatible duties, but with the vague boundaries of what counts as logic. The vagueness of these boundaries (and its implications for the alleged logical gap between Is and Ought) is discussed in Hage 2025.
37. A more extensive account of the logic for reasons (Reason-based Logic) can be found in Hage 1997: 130-170 and – less extensive, but logically more precise – in Hage 2005: 69-99.
38. A single reason can consist of more than one fact.
39. This implies that she also ought to use pesticides to that purpose. See section 5.1.
40. That this is a reason against combatting thistles needs supporting argumentation, which most likely would include the (controversial) claim that thistles can only be combatted by using pesticides.
41. In this paper, that duties to perform some action are reasons why the agents of these duties ought to perform these actions is assumed to be a matter of logic.
42. The latter conclusion can be drawn by *default*: if no other reasons have been shown to be present, it is assumed that there are no other reasons. The specification of the sets of reasons pleading for or against a thesis leads us into the territory of reasoning by default, but in this paper that territory will remain a no-go-area.
43. The logic for reasoning about the relative weight of two sets of reasons is discussed in Hage 2005: 101-134.
44. Technically, this result can be reached by assuming that any non-empty set of reasons outweighs the empty set of reasons. ‘The’ empty set, because sets that have the same elements are identical. Two sets that both have no elements have the same elements and are therefore the same set. There is only one empty set, *the* empty set.
45. In ethical and legal theory there is an extensive literature on the nature of reasons, which includes Raz 1999, Redondo 1999, Alvarez 2010 and Scanlon 2014. Wegner 2002 and Mercier and Sperber 2017 provide important different perspectives from cognitive science.
46. A more extensive account of the logic of rules can be found in Hage 2005: 87-95. I presently consider the account in Hage 1997 as outdated.
47. The word ‘valid’ can be used in different senses, and the identification here of validity with existence is no more than a stipulative definition for the purpose of the present paper.
48. Some conditions may be implicit. The typical case is *scope conditions*, which limit the applicability of rules in space, in time, or to particular categories of persons. See Hage 1997: 107-109.
49. This common situation is why reasoning with rules looks so much like Modus Ponens-style arguments. That appearance is deceptive. It is also harmful because it can lead to thoughtless application of applicable rules, or to needless claims that rules have silent conditions which are not satisfied if the application of the rule is undesirable.
50. There can also be reasons why a rule applies to a case that are different from the fact that the rule is applicable to the case. That may be the case, for instance, if the case falls under the purpose but not under the conditions of the rule. If the rule applies without being applicable, we often speak of *analogous rule application*. See Verheij and Hage 1994 and Hage 1997: 118-121.
51. There are at least two ways in which rules can conflict. One way, discussed in section 4.2, is when application of the conflicting rules would lead to a conflict of compliance. The other is when the consequences of the rules logically contradict each other. This would occur, for instance, if both the (simplified) rules that thieves are punishable and that minors are not punishable would apply to a case.
52. These two ways resemble the distinction between undercutters and rebutters that was introduced by Pollock 1987.
53. The first difference was that the content of obligations is typically determined, not by the norms, but by the events that gave rise to them. See section 3.2.

54. This gives rise to a discussion of whether there is a logical difference between duties and obligations or whether the difference is ‘merely’ a matter of law. The discussion raises the follow-up question of whether the distinction between logical and legal differences is a strict one.

55. The issue of deontic inheritance in relation to permitted-to-do facts will be addressed briefly in section 6.5.

56. It is tempting to analyse the involvement relation between action types as some sort of logical relation. Given the vague boundaries of what counts as logic, this is possible. However, action types are logically speaking individuals, and it is not usual to treat relations between individuals as logical. In this paper, I ‘solve’ this problem by the use of a two-place predicate ‘involves’, that takes two action types as its parameters. As usual in this paper, the treatment is informal.

57. All these differences can have implications for the strength of the logical relations between the ought-to-do facts. Exploring these differences – and the very idea that logical relations have a characteristic *strength* – is beyond the scope of the present paper.

58. Personally, I prefer not to accept logical inferences from the relation between action types to the relation between duties. On my view, if action-type_1 involves action-type_2, the existence of a duty for agent A to perform action-type 1 is a *reason* why A ought to perform action-type_2, but this reason is not necessarily a duty to perform action_type_2. However, see the discussion in the next subsection regarding the relation between *recurrent duties* and *one-shot duties*.

59. Hansson 2013 provides an overview of many issues involved in permission as discussed in the literature on deontic logic.

60. The reason we have a word for this kind of nothing is that the absence of an ought-to-do fact is meaningful for language-users (people). Compare it to health: health is nothing except the absence of illness. Because this absence is important for people, we have a word for it.

61. I got this ‘knowledge’ from Chat GPT. When I asked for a reference, the software declared the following:

“I didn’t pull it from a website or quote a source. It’s a synthesis based on widely known Bond lore and how writers use the ‘license to kill’ idea as a narrative device”.

62. Notice that this interprets so-called ‘conflict rules’ as rules for determining what reason outweighs the applicability of a rule as a reason for the application of that rule.

63. For more details, see Hage 2018: 237-240, and Hage 2024.

64. A lawyer would typically not use the word “permitted” to describe the legal status of the act. The word used in the example – “lawful” – is more common, even though it means the same as “legally permitted”.

65. For instance, the starting point for all arguments about the lawfulness of act tokens is that an act token was lawful unless it was performed by an agent and instantiated an action type, such that this agent ought to have refrained from this action type. Aleida’s use of pesticides was *pro tanto* unlawful because Aleida ought to have refrained from using pesticides.

ABSTRACTS

Deontic logic is the logic of what ought to be done, or what ought to be the case. In this paper, I attempt to bring deontic logic closer to the interests of theoretically interested lawyers. To that end, I use examples of deontic reasoning that, although simplified for expository purposes,

resemble real legal arguments. Moreover, I refrain from formalisation. It is possible to distinguish three 'steps' of deontic reasoning, and these three steps structure the argument of this paper. The first step is from non-deontic facts to the duties (or obligations) an agent has. The second step is from duties to what an agent (legally) ought to do. And the third step is from what an agent ought to do to whether an act performed by the agent was lawful or not. Deontic logic is a broad subject, and I had to be selective in the topics that are addressed. The selected topics are the structure of ought-to-do facts (section 2); norms, duties, obligations and what an agent ought to do (section 3); reasoning with norms (section 4); deontic inheritance (section 5); and three kinds of permission (section 6). The conclusion of the paper lists differences between other treatments of deontic logic and the present approach.

Deontična logika za pravnike. Deontična logika je logika tistega, kar bi moralo biti storjeno oziroma kar bi moralo veljati. V prispevku skušam deontično logiko približati interesom teoretično usmerjenih pravnikov. V ta namen uporabljam primere deontičnega sklepanja, ki so sicer poenostavljeni zaradi razlage, vendar so podobni dejanskim pravnim argumentom. Poleg tega se izogibam formalizaciji. Razločiti je mogoče tri »korake« deontičnega sklepanja, ki strukturirajo razpravo v tem članku. Prvi korak vodi od nedeontičnih dejstev k dolžnostim (oziroma obveznostim), ki jih ima določen subjekt. Drugi korak vodi od dolžnosti k temu, kaj bi subjekt (pravno) moral storiti. Tretji korak pa vodi od tega, kaj bi subjekt moral storiti, k presoji, ali je bilo dejanje, ki ga je subjekt opravil, zakonito ali ne. Deontična logika je široko področje, zato je bilo treba opraviti izbor obravnavanih tem. Izbrane teme so: struktura dejstev o tem, kaj bi bilo treba storiti (2. poglavje); norme, dolžnosti, obveznosti in to, kaj bi subjekt moral storiti (3. poglavje); sklepanje z normami (4. poglavje); deontična dednost (5. poglavje); ter tri vrste dovoljenja (6. poglavje). V sklepu so navedene razlike med drugimi obravnavami deontične logike in pristopom, predstavljenim v tem prispevku.

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motslessl tehtanje razlogov, deontična dednost, dolžnosti, tisto, kar bi bilo treba storiti, dovoljenje

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